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AI AND IOT BASED PARKINSON'S DISEASE PREDICTION AND MONITORING SYSTEM

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Abstract— Parkinson's disease is a progressive neurological disorder that affects movement, muscle control, and coordination, making early detection and continuous monitoring critical. Traditional diagnosis often depends on clinical observation, which may fail to capture subtle or early-stage symptoms. This project proposes an AI and IoT-based system that utilizes wearable sensors to monitor physiological and motion-related parameters, including heart rate, muscle activity (EMG), and hand tremors (MEMS). The system integrates these sensors with a NodeMCU microcontroller to collect real-time data, which is subsequently processed using a Python-based backend. An XGBoost machine learning model analyzes the synchronized data to predict the likelihood of Parkinson's disease. Results are visualized through a Streamlit dashboard, while a buzzer and LCD provide instant local alerts. This low-cost, portable solution aims to support early detection, continuous monitoring, and enhanced healthcare assistance for Parkinson's patients.

Index Terms— Parkinson's Disease, IoT, XGBoost, Machine Learning, NodeMCU, Remote Monitoring, EMG Sensor, MEMS Sensor, Healthcare AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder that primarily affects the motor system, leading to symptoms such as tremors, rigidity, bradykinesia, and impaired balance. The global prevalence of Parkinson's disease is increasing, particularly among the aging population, creating a significant need for effective diagnostic and monitoring solutions. Conventional diagnostic approaches are largely based on clinical evaluations and patient history, which rely on periodic hospital visits and subjective assessment by medical professionals. These methods often fail to detect early-stage symptoms and do not provide continuous monitoring of the patient's condition in real-time environments.

Recent advancements in technology, particularly in the fields of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT), have opened new opportunities for improving healthcare systems. IoT-enabled wearable devices facilitate continuous data collection from patients, including physiological and motion-related parameters such as heart rate, tremors, and muscle activity.

At the same time, AI techniques enable intelligent analysis of large volumes of data, allowing for accurate prediction and early diagnosis of diseases. The integration of these technologies provides a promising approach for enhancing the detection and monitoring of Parkinson's disease.

Several existing systems have attempted to utilize machine learning algorithms and sensor-based data for Parkinson's disease detection. However, many of these systems lack real-time monitoring capabilities, efficient data transmission mechanisms, and accurate predictive models. Additionally, they often do not provide user-friendly interfaces or immediate alert systems, which are essential for effective patient care and timely medical intervention.

To overcome these limitations, this paper proposes an AI and IoT-based Parkinson's disease prediction and monitoring system. The proposed system employs wearable sensors such as heart rate sensors, electromyography (EMG) sensors, and MEMS-based motion sensors to continuously collect patient data. The collected data is transmitted wirelessly using a NodeMCU microcontroller to a cloud-based platform, where it is processed and analyzed using the XGBoost machine learning algorithm for accurate prediction. The system also provides real-time monitoring through a Streamlit-based dashboard and generates alerts using a buzzer and LCD display in case of abnormal conditions. By integrating IoT and AI technologies, the proposed system aims to enable early detection, continuous monitoring, and improved healthcare support for Parkinson's patients.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Recent studies demonstrate the effectiveness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in healthcare monitoring and neurological disorder detection. For instance, El Gedawy et al. (2023) explored deep learning techniques for analyzing EEG signals in medical applications. Rahman et al. (2022) achieved high accuracy in Parkinson's disease detection using voice

and movement-based datasets with machine learning algorithms. Similarly, Sakar et al. (2019) utilized biomedical voice measurements to improve classification performance in PD diagnosis.

IoT-based healthcare monitoring systems have also gained significant attention for enabling continuous and remote patient tracking. Systems developed by Sharma and Gupta (2021) and Patel and Shah (2022) demonstrated the use of wearable sensors for real-time monitoring of physiological parameters such as heart rate and motion patterns. These systems improve accessibility and reduce the need for frequent hospital visits; however, they often lack advanced predictive capabilities.

Recent research has focused on integrating IoT with machine learning to enhance disease prediction accuracy. For example, Kaur et al. (2021) proposed a hybrid system combining sensor data with classification algorithms for early detection of Parkinson's disease. Despite these advancements, challenges such as limited accuracy, lack of real-time alert mechanisms, and inefficient data visualization still exist.

Our proposed system builds upon these existing approaches by integrating multiple sensors and utilizing the XGBoost algorithm for high-precision prediction. Additionally, the system provides real-time monitoring through a cloud-based dashboard and incorporates an alert mechanism, thereby offering an efficient and comprehensive solution for Parkinson's disease prediction and management.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system adopts a systematic hardware- software integration approach. The system is divided into six functional modules:

- 1) **Sensor Data Collection:** Continuous acquisition of physiological parameters such as heart rate, EMG signals, and MEMS-based motion data. The analog signals are converted into digital form for further processing.
- 2) **Data Transmission:** Utilizes NodeMCU (ESP8266) for wireless transmission of sensor data to the IoT cloud platform using Wi-Fi connectivity.
- 3) **Data Processing:** Involves noise filtering, normalization, and feature extraction to identify relevant patterns such as tremor frequency and irregular muscle activity.
- 4) **Prediction Module:** The core AI component uses the XGBoost algorithm to classify and predict the likelihood of Parkinson's disease based on trained datasets.
- 5) **User Interface:** A Streamlit-based dashboard is used to display real-time data visualization for doctors and caregivers.
- 6) **Alert & Notification:** A buzzer and I2C LCD

are used to provide alerts when abnormal conditions such as excessive tremors or irregular heart rate are detected.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig.1.Architecture Diagram

The system architecture is divided into four primary layers, as illustrated in Fig. 1 each responsible for a specific function in the overall system.

A. Perception Layer:

The perception layer consists of wearable sensors such as **heart rate sensors**, **EMG sensors**, and **MEMS-based motion sensors**. These sensors continuously collect physiological and movement-related data from the patient, including tremors, muscle activity, and heart rate. The collected analog signals are converted into digital form for further processing.

B. Transport Layer:

The transport layer is responsible for transmitting the collected sensor data to the cloud. It utilizes the **NodeMCU (ESP8266)** microcontroller, which provides Wi-Fi connectivity for real-time data transfer. This layer ensures reliable and continuous communication between the hardware components and the cloud platform.

C. Processing Layer:

In this layer, the received data is processed and analyzed. It includes preprocessing steps such as noise filtering, normalization, and feature extraction to obtain meaningful information from raw sensor data. The processed data is then fed into the **XGBoost**

machine learning algorithm, which predicts the likelihood and severity of Parkinson's disease.

D. Application Layer:

The application layer provides the user interface and alert mechanisms. A **Streamlit-based dashboard** is used to visualize real-time data and prediction results for doctors and caregivers. Additionally, an alert system using a buzzer and **LCD display** notifies users when abnormal conditions such as excessive tremors or irregular heart rate are detected.

V. TECHNOLOGIES AND HARDWARE

The proposed system utilizes a combination of hardware components and software technologies to enable efficient data acquisition, processing, and real-time monitoring of Parkinson's disease.

A. Hardware Components:

The hardware implementation includes NodeMCU (ESP8266) as the main microcontroller for data transmission. Various sensors such as heart rate sensors, EMG sensors, and MEMS-based motion sensors are used to collect physiological and movement-related data from the patient. Additionally, an I2C LCD display and a buzzer are integrated to provide real-time alerts and notifications in case of abnormal conditions.

B. Software Technologies:

The software framework consists of Python for backend processing and machine learning model implementation.

The XGBoost algorithm is used for accurate prediction of Parkinson's disease based on the processed sensor data. A Streamlit-based dashboard is developed to provide real-time visualization and monitoring of patient data. Cloud platforms are used for data storage and remote access.

C. Communication Technology:

Wi-Fi communication is enabled through the NodeMCU module, allowing seamless transmission of sensor data to the cloud. This ensures continuous monitoring and real-time data availability for analysis and prediction.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed system successfully demonstrates real-time data acquisition, transmission, and visualization of physiological parameters. The sensor data obtained from heart rate, EMG, and MEMS sensors was effectively processed and analyzed using the XGBoost algorithm. The model was able to accurately identify patterns associated with Parkinson's disease, particularly tremor frequency and irregular motor activity, enabling clear differentiation between normal and affected conditions.

Fig.2.Heart Rate Signal

The system successfully captures real-time physiological data using EMG, MEMS, and pulse sensors. The collected values include heart rate, SpO2 levels, muscle activity, and tremor signals. The observed heart rate values are within the normal range (around 78 BPM), and SpO2 levels are approximately 96%, indicating stable oxygen saturation. The EMG sensor outputs measurable muscle activity, while the MEMS sensor captures small but continuous tremor movements. These results confirm that the sensors are functioning accurately and reliably. The heart rate signal shows minor variations over time, which is expected in normal physiological conditions. These patterns are essential for distinguishing between normal and abnormal behavior

Fig.3.EMG Signal

The graphical representation of sensor data shows clear patterns in each signal. The tremor signal obtained from the MEMS sensor exhibits periodic oscillations, indicating involuntary hand movements. Similarly, the EMG signal

displays fluctuating amplitudes representing muscle contractions and relaxations.

Fig.4.MEMS Signal

Fig.5.Pediction Dashboard

The Streamlit-based dashboard provides a clear and interactive interface for displaying real-time sensor data and predictions. It shows parameters such as heart rate, SpO2 level, and EMG values along with graphical plots of signals. The dashboard also highlights the final prediction result, making it easy for users and healthcare professionals to interpret the data quickly.

VII. COMPARSION WITH EXISTING SYSTEM

Table I summarises the key differentiators between the proposed system and existing system.

TABLE I
DIFFERENCE BETWEEN EXISTING SYSTEM AND PROPOSED SYSTEM

Feature	Existing System	Proposed System
Detection Method	Manual clinical observation	AI-based prediction using XGBoost
Monitoring	Periodic (hospital visits only)	Continuous real-time monitoring
Data Collection	Limited or manual	Automatic using wearable sensors (EMG, Heart rate, MEMS)
Early Detection	Difficult	Possible with machine learning analysis
Accuracy	Moderate	High accuracy
Real-Time Analysis	Not available	Available
Remote Monitoring	Not supported	Supported via IoT (NodeMCU + Cloud)
Alert System	Not available	Available (Buzzer & LCD alerts)
User Interface	Minimal or none	Interactive dashboard (Streamlit)
Cost Efficiency	Higher (hospital dependency)	Low-cost and portable solution

VIII. CONCLUSION

The proposed AI and IoT-based Parkinson's disease prediction system successfully demonstrates an efficient approach for real-time health monitoring and early detection. The system integrates multiple sensors such as EMG, MEMS, and pulse sensors to continuously collect physiological data related to muscle activity, tremors, heart rate, and oxygen levels.

The collected data is transmitted through the NodeMCU to the cloud, where it is processed and analyzed using the XGBoost machine learning algorithm. The model effectively identifies patterns associated with Parkinson's disease and provides accurate predictions. The Streamlit-based dashboard enables clear visualization of real-time data and prediction results, making the system user-friendly and accessible.

Furthermore, the system is cost-effective, portable, and suitable for deployment in remote and resource-limited environments. The inclusion of an alert mechanism enhances patient safety by providing immediate notification in case of abnormal conditions. Overall, the proposed system proves to be reliable, scalable, and practical for continuous monitoring and early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease.

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